

A FURTHER LINK BETWEEN LABORATORY ANALYSIS AND INDUSTRIAL PROCESS OPTIMIZATION - THE SIZE EFFECT ON DRYING REFRACTORY CASTABLES

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic materials display different special features such as refractoriness, erosion and corrosion resistance and, nowadays, increased attention has been given to its energy barrier capabilities. However, one of its most important features is its capability of being used for building structures several meters long, weighting multiple tons. Hydraulic bonded castables need to be carefully dried in order to prevent explosive spalling due to pressurization of water vapor. Usually, this process is studied in laboratory conditions within controlled environments on samples with few centimeters. The large discrepancy between such size scales can be one of the reasons why even though drying is a broadly studied subject, the industrial practice is still based on semi-empirical rules. Thus, the current work focused on better understanding the effect of the sample volume in its mass loss behavior. That was attained by using conventional (5 cm x 5 cm cylindric samples) and macro thermogravimetry tests (with 20 x 20 x 20 cm³ and 30 x 30 x 30 cm³ cubic samples) for compositions with and without polymeric fibers. The results pointed out that the difference in size led to distinct thermal gradients within the sample, and different temperatures of changes on the inflection of the sample's heating rate. Different mass loss profiles were observed, especially considering the sample without the drying additives. These results show that when modelling the drying of the lining of industrial equipment, besides considering of the heating protocol the volume of the object needs to be accounted for.

INTRODUCTION

Steel and cement are two of the most used materials in the world [1]. With a production that correlates directly with a country's GDP [2], it is only natural that the production scale of such crucial products is in the range of 1500 Mtons per year [2]. To enable such a large-scale production while ensuring safety and, most importantly, profitability, refractories play a crucial role. They are used to line large structures that span several meters in length and weigh multiple tons.

Refractory castables are a special class of materials well-suited for such applications, particularly in this context thanks to their capacity of being shaped into complex geometries [3] and their higher installation rates when comparing to shaped products [4].

The hydraulic bonded compositions, which are one of the most common categories within the refractory castables [4], have one important drawback. Prior to reaching their operation temperatures they require a careful drying process [5, 6, 7], which can be time-consuming and even dangerous in case of explosive spalling.

This phenomenon takes place when the combination of stresses resulted from the pressurization of water vapor within the castables pores with the thermomechanical solicitations surpasses the materials' strength, leading to crack propagation and even thrusting pieces of the lining [8].

Ever since the refractory castables' composition particle packing was optimized with the objective of maximizing their mechanical strength and corrosion resistance, leading to smaller permeability levels and, consequently, increased likelihood of facing explosive spalling, efforts have been made to mitigate this phenomenon. These included the addition of polymeric fibers, metallic additives, and implementation of longer heating curves, with fixed temperature plateaus, relying on empirical observations [5]. However, these approaches are still far from optimizing this costly and energy-intensive process, as demonstrated by Cunha et al. [7].

All of these developments have been primarily based on observations of samples at the laboratory scale, or, rarely, on pilot scale. Notably, there is currently a lack of research available (to the best of the authors' knowledge) related to the behavior of drying of refractory castables in real-world industrial structures. Consequently, it is essential to acknowledge the potential existence of mechanisms that may be influenced by size effects, which might not be visualized when only smaller samples are considered.

It is well documented and understood that the observed strength of samples of a given material are inversely proportional to their volumes. However, deviations from the empirical law initially established by Galileo (which states that nominal stress is determined by the ratio of the load to the square of the characteristic dimension of the structure) indicate the presence of what is called a "size effect" [9]. This phenomenon can arise from either statistical or energetic factors. The statistical cause is associated with the Weibull probability, which represents the likelihood of encountering a critical defect within the material under a given solicitation. On the other hand, the energetic cause relates to the relationship between the volume of the fracture process zone (a region ahead of the crack tip where energy dissipation can occur without increasing the crack's length) and the volume of the sample itself. [9].

Another instance where the body size also exerts an effect in its overall behavior was detected by Alarcon-Ruiz et al. [10], where different volumes of samples with the same Portland cement concrete composition led to changes in the measurements of intrinsic permeability.

Finally, the thermal transport within a material is highly dependent on its size and this can be directly visualized by the Fourier number given in Equation 1 [11].

$$Fo = \frac{\alpha t}{L^2} \quad (1)$$

where α is the thermal diffusivity, t is time and L is the characteristic length through which effective thermal conduction occurs.

For the same material and the same time length (that is, fixing α and t in Equation 1), the larger the material (L), the smaller is the resulting Fourier number, which means that during heating, a significant temperature increase can only be observed in a small region next to the surface that is being heated, and longer times are needed to reach a stationary state [11].

Thus, the increase of size of a given sample will directly impact on its thermal state, leading to different thermal gradients, even in the case of having the exact same heat input in the system. As the drying stages are strongly linked to the refractory's temperature, this will show an additional complexity when the size effects are considered on the refractory drying.

Finally, it should be also noted that these changes in the thermal gradient will have major implications on the thermomechanical stresses developed during the material's heating, further linking the sample's size to its likelihood of facing explosive spalling.

In light of these considerations, the objectives of the current work are threefold. Firstly, macro thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) will be deployed to investigate the size effect on the spalling behavior of refractory materials. This analysis will provide valuable insights into how the size of a material affects its thermal response and propensity for spalling. Secondly, the focus will be on describing the occurrence of moisture condensation at the innermost positions of the macro TGA samples, seen as a kink in the temperature increase

at such positions, and also correlating this with other observations in the literature. Lastly, the effect of incorporating fibers into refractory materials will be compared and evaluated to determine their influence on spalling behavior, and its effectiveness in improving the material's drying on samples of different sizes. By addressing these objectives, this research aims to advance the understanding of spalling phenomena in refractory materials and provide insights for optimizing their performance and durability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigations were carried out considering a high alumina castable containing 5 wt.% of calcium aluminate cement, commonly known as 5CAC, with a distribution coefficient (q) of 0.21, as per the Andreasen's particle packing model, either containing or not 0.1 wt.% polymeric fibers (EMSIL Dry, Elkem). The detailed composition of the castables is provided in Table 1.

Tab. 1: 5CAC and 5CAC-ED high-alumina refractory castables compositions.

Raw Materials		5CAC (wt.%)	5CAC-ED (wt.%)
Tabular Alumina (Almatis)	AT 6-3	18	18
	AT 3-1	10	10
	AT 1-0.5	11	11
	AT 0.6-0.2	9	9
	AT 0.2-0	16	16
	AT<45	10	10
Calcined and reactive alumina	CL370, Almatis	11	11
	CT3000SG, Almatis	10	10
Calcium Aluminate Cement	Secar 71, Imerys	5.00	5.00
Polymeric Fiber	EMSIL Dry, Elkem	-	0.10
Distilled Water		5.00	5.25
Dispersant	Castement FS60, Basf	0.20	0.20

The powders were first mixed for 1 minute, and the water was gradually added over a span of 3 minutes. Subsequently, the prepared sample was either poured into cylindrical molds measuring 50 mm in diameter and 50 mm in height for conventional TGA tests or molded into a 30 x 30 x 30 cm³ or 20 x 20 x 20 cm³ cube for Macro TGA analyses. Following this, the samples underwent a 24-hour curing period at room temperature inside sealed plastic bags, containing a water-filled container to maintain a humid environment. Subsequently, the TGA tests were conducted according to the experimental setup outlined in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: TGA experiments layout for the (a) conventional sized samples and (b) macro TGA. The schematics are not at real scale.

The heating rates applied were 2°C/min for the conventional-sized samples and 0.83°C/min for the macro TGA. The mass loss curve was obtained using Equation 2, while its derivative with respect to temperature was computed applying the central finite difference approximation described in Equation 3.

$$W(\%) = 100 \times \left(\frac{M_o - M}{M_o - M_f} \right) \quad (2)$$

where M_o is the initial mass, M_f is the mass at the end of the test.

$$\left(\frac{dW}{dT} \right)_i = \frac{W_{i+1} - W_{i-1}}{T_{i+1} - T_{i-1}} \quad (3)$$

where W_{i+1} and T_{i+1} is the mass and temperature at time instant $i+1$, and conversely, W_{i-1} and T_{i-1} are such values at the earlier moment $i-1$. The temperature derivative is also calculated using the same methodology.

Finally, Table 2 summarizes all tests conducted in this study, highlighting the conditions and the samples considered. The characteristic length is used as a shorter notation for the sample's volume, corresponding to the cubes' size for the macro TGA samples and for the diameter of the conventional TGA ones.

Tab. 2: Tests conducted in the present work.

Test	TGA Equipment	Heating Rate	Composition	Shape	Characteristic Length, ℓ
1	Conventional	2°C/min	5CAC	Cylinder	5cm
2	Macro TGA	0.83°C/min	5CAC	Cube	30cm
3	Macro TGA	0.83°C/min	5CAC	Cube	20cm
4	Conventional	2°C/min	5CAC-ED	Cylinder	5cm
5	Macro TGA	0.83°C/min	5CAC-ED	Cube	30cm
6	Macro TGA	0.83°C/min	5CAC-ED	Cube	20cm

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 describes the sample temperature evolution for all the tests, either the reference and fiber-containing ones in a) and b), respectively.

Fig. 2: Temperature evolution for the without (a) or with polymeric fibers (b). The $\ell = 30$ cm samples had embedded multiple thermocouples aligned at different heights at the center of the sample (TC Bottom – $h=5$ cm, TC Middle – $h=15$ cm, TC Top – $h=25$ cm). For the other samples the thermocouple was placed on the samples' center of mass. Kinks on the temperature increase curves are highlighted with circles.

The sample tested with the conventional TGA equipment shows a faster heating rate thanks to the higher scheduled furnace temperature increase. It is possible to observe that from room temperature up to 180°C, the temperature increase is dictated by the thermal conduction of the sample, which controls how fast the incident energy from the radiant heater increases the temperature at the center of the sample. After that, the temperature increases

linearly, as seen for both the samples without and with fibers in a) and b), respectively.

The results of the macro TGA tests show specific features, only seen on the large-scale samples, such as the presence of kinks on the temperature increase curves. This trend was reproducible occurring at roughly the same temperatures as shown on duplicate tests, and only took place during the first heating of the sample, as it was checked that the second heating behavior was linear in time (results not shown here).

Additionally, as can be seen on the $\ell = 30\text{cm}$ results for the thermocouples placed at different positions, those abrupt changes of temperature increase rate are only observed at the samples' center and are not observed for the positions 10cm away from it.

This phenomenon seems to be consistent in temperature even for samples of different sizes, being only delayed for the larger bodies thanks to their larger thermal inertia. Also, after the first large kink, a second one can be observed for higher temperatures.

When comparing the results of compositions without fibers and those with in Figures 1 a) and 1 b), it is also possible to notice that the temperatures at which this event occurs are smaller for the samples with the drying additives.

To better understand this trend, Figure 3 presents the mass loss rate and the temperature derivative with respect to time plotted over the same graph for the samples with $\ell = 30\text{cm}$. It is highlighted with vertical lines the moment when the largest kink (the first one) on the temperature evolution profiles is observed. It is possible to highlight that for both compositions the phenomenon takes place exactly after the peak of mass loss, when the largest amount of water is removed.

Fig. 3: Temperature derivative with respect to time and mass loss rate evolution in time for the samples $\ell = 30\text{cm}$ without (a) or with polymeric fibers (b). The time when the largest kinks on the temperature increase curves are highlighted with vertical lines.

Thus, this phenomenon is related to the mass transfer of water that occurs inside the sample, which itself is highly affected by the

presence of the drying additives, leading to kinks at distinct temperatures for the sample containing polymeric fibers.

One hypothesis to explain this phenomenon is the entrapment of liquid water at the innermost position of the sample, which can evaporate as the pressurization decays. Multiple observations can support this hypothesis: i) Auvray et al. [12] reported that differences in hydrates formed during an explosion test of a calcium aluminate sample castable were the results of a reaction under hydrothermal conditions, indicating that such a region had a high concentration of water; ii) Khoeller et al. [13] mentioned that the hydrothermal conditions that occur during drying change the phase composition and microstructure of the castables; and iii) Moreira et al. [14] proved that moisture accumulation occurs even when considering small samples during neutron tomography observation of drying, detecting an increase of water at the innermost positions.

Providing further description of the possible explanation, Figure 4 presents a portion of the phase diagram of water based on the Clausius–Clapeyron relation [15]. It is possible to observe that at the temperature which the kink is observed the pressure required to maintain water as liquid at the center of the sample with fiber is 1.6 MPa, whereas for the sample without any additive, this value is 7.4 MPa.

Fig. 4: Phase diagram of water showing the locus of the largest thermal kinks observed for the samples with and without polymeric fibers.

As the pressure is reduced below such values and the dry out step proceeds, the liquid water suddenly vaporizes consuming the thermal energy to undergo the phase transition. When the water is removed the effective specific heat of the castable is reduced and the heating rate at the center of the sample is increased.

This sudden release of water molecules can lead to re-pressurization of the gas within the pores and justify the second kink observed at larger temperatures. Such an observation is crucial as it shows that using only conventional thermogravimetry to study the drying, important phenomena might not be observed thanks to a scale effect.

The impact of the sample volume and the polymeric fiber can be also observed on the mass loss presented in Figure 5. It is possible to see that the drying is progressively slower as the sample size is increased. The difference, however, is smaller when considering the composition containing the fibers. This is directly linked with the faster drying promoted by the increased permeability thanks to the fibers melting and burnout [5].

The possibility of removing water through the newly formed network enables the drying to be less prone to the scale effect. The larger permeability also leads to the smaller thermal kink observed in Figure 2, due the smaller pressures that occur at the innermost position of the sample.

Fig. 5: Mass loss of the samples without (a) and with polymeric fibers (b) for the macro TGA (MTGA) and conventional thermogravimetry (CTGA) of samples with characteristic lengths $\ell = 30\text{cm}$, $\ell = 20\text{cm}$ and $\ell = 5\text{cm}$.

CONCLUSIONS

The manufacturing process of crucial materials such as steel and cement rely on the performance of refractory materials structures several meters long, weighting multiple tons. They require high green strength obtained by different binders, and one of the most common classes, the hydraulic bonded castables, such as calcium aluminate cement, might undergo explosive spalling during its drying.

Hence this process is usually slowly carried out with the aid of temperature plateaus and drying additives, such as polymeric fibers. Even though several studies have been investigating this research topic, the reproduction of the large industrial scales are impossible at laboratory conditions and any characterization or experiment is done on smaller samples.

The current work aimed to study the effect of the sample volume on the drying process of refractory castable. That was achieved with the help of a macro thermogravimetry equipment.

It was found out that specific phenomena were only observed on tests conducted with larger samples, such as the appearance of a kink on the temperature evolution at the innermost position of the sample. This feature was not observed by thermocouples placed 10cm away from the samples' center of mass.

This observation could be explained by the sudden evaporation of water that occurs as the material is dried and the vapor pressure is reduced. Several observations from the literature such as evidence of hydrothermal hydration at the innermost positions of exploded castables as well as the *in-situ* observation of moisture accumulation at the center of refractory castables also support such explanation.

Compositions containing polymeric fibers displayed the thermal kink at lower temperatures. Also, their presence led to faster drying, and most importantly, the scale effect observed on such samples was less intense than that seen for the reference composition with no drying additives.

This study highlighted a framework to consistently study the effect of different volumes on the drying behavior of refractory castables promoting a better approximation between the industrial reality and the laboratory experimentation. In a near future it is expected that semi-empirical general laws could be obtained

providing helpful guidelines for the design of safe and efficient drying profiles.

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